

A System for Evaluating Autonomous Driving Algorithms via Gaussian Splatting and Mesh Representation

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Abstract—This paper presents a system for capturing and representing spatial data extracted from an autonomous vehicle equipped with dual frontal cameras with limited overlapping field of view, LiDAR and wheel sensors. The methodology includes a sequence of steps to process data into a meaningful representation for simulation: initial image and camera pose capture, pose refinement, offline multi-view stereo reconstruction and Gaussian Splatting model extraction. By minimizing camera overlap, the system maximizes the quantity of spatial information captured. The resulting mesh and Gaussian Splatting point cloud enable realistic simulations, providing a robust framework for testing and evaluating autonomous driving systems.

Index Terms—Bundle Adjustment, Multi-View Stereo, Gaussian Splatting, Autonomous Driving

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the evaluation of autonomous driving algorithms has gained significant traction. To effectively address a wide range of scenarios, a diverse dataset [1], [2] is essential for successfully training and evaluating algorithms for autonomous driving. This paper introduces a comprehensive system designed to capture data and process them into meaningful representation such as meshes and Gaussian Splatting point clouds [3]. The output mesh can be employed to test and evaluate motion planning and localization (see Fig. 1). The Gaussian splatting model can be highly effective in generating realistic images in real time, serving as a component for assessing the performance of image classification, object detection, object tracking, semantic segmentation, and instance segmentation algorithms in the context of autonomous driving systems. We recorded all the images captured by the cameras together with raw estimated pose extracted using data from LiDAR and wheel sensors.

II. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The proposed system (see Fig. 2) consists of a vehicle equipped for capturing data and several interconnected

components to process it, producing a high-fidelity mesh and a Gaussian Splatting point cloud suitable for simulation and testing.

A. Sensor Configuration

The system is anchored by a vehicle equipped with two frontal cameras, which are positioned in order to have minimal overlapping fields of view. This configuration maximizes the information captured from the surrounding environment. The downside of this approach is that 3D reconstructions algorithms struggle much more in this scenario, however the issue in our case is mitigated by capturing a sufficient number of images and the additional data supplied by other sensors. The vehicle is outfitted with a LiDAR sensor and wheel sensors (IMU) which can provide a rough estimation of the current position of the vehicle in the environment. The cameras are already calibrated relatively to the vehicle's frame and LiDAR sensor using [8], ensuring an accurate pose transform between the two cameras.

B. Pose Estimation Refinement

Captured images and raw pose estimates serve as inputs for feature matching and bundle adjustment. This step allows to obtain more accurate camera poses which drastically improve both the multi-view stereo (MVS) and Gaussian splatting reconstructions.

C. Multi-View Stereo and Mesh Generation

Once refined poses are acquired, they, along with the captured images, are utilized as inputs for the multi-view stereo algorithm. The core algorithm is based on the MVS method proposed in [4]. From the output point cloud a mesh is extracted using the Screened Poisson Surface Reconstruction method [5]. This process allows to create a continuous surface representation of the observed environment, which is crucial for simulation applications.

Fig. 1. From left to right: vehicle employed for image acquisition, example of mesh output and algorithm evaluation.

Fig. 2. Data capture and processing pipeline.

D. Training a Gaussian Splatting Representation

Gaussian splatting is a novel rendering technique that represents 3D scenes using a collection of Gaussian functions. This method represents the underlying geometry through continuous 3D Gaussian functions, allowing for efficient and high-quality rendering. Each point in the cloud is represented by a function that encodes information about its position, color, and size, retaining properties of continuous volumetric radiance field. The technique excels in producing realistic visuals at real time due to the rasterization approach in contrast to the slower NeRF [6]. Input images, refined camera poses and the point cloud extracted from the MVS step are used to train a Gaussian splatting representation. This representation allows for the efficient rendering of scenes and the generation of high-quality images, which can be utilized for testing and validating computer vision algorithms for autonomous driving applications.

III. APPLICATIONS

The resulting mesh can be seamlessly integrated into simulation environments, such as Gazebo [10], allowing researchers and developers to conduct realistic testing scenarios. Furthermore, rendered images obtained from the Gaussian splatting representation provide a rich dataset for evaluating various computer vision techniques, contributing to the advancement of autonomous driving technology. Preliminary tests were performed on algorithms such as YOLOv9 [9] and HDL [7] (see Fig. 1).

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a systematic approach to processing and representing data for evaluating autonomous driving algorithms. By leveraging techniques such as feature matching,

bundle adjustment, multi-view stereo, and Gaussian splatting, the proposed system produces high-fidelity outputs that are invaluable for simulation and testing in the field of computer vision. Images rendered with Gaussian splatting help bridge the gap between simulation and real-world testing, enabling more meaningful and accurate simulations.

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